

IMPORTANCE OF ORGANIZING SMART AUDIENCES BASED ON INNOVATIVE CHANGES IN ENSURING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN PROFESSIONAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Avliyakov A.K.

Candidate of pedagogical sciences, Associate Professor, Department of management in education, Institute of Professional Education Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *The article examines the content of the concepts on quality of education, factors influencing the quality of education, smart education, smart audience, innovative approach. The importance of ensuring the quality of education through the organization of smart classrooms based on innovative changes has also been revealed and the requirements for teachers in this process have been determined.*

Keywords: *smart audience, smart education, innovative approach, multimedia tools, quality of education, educational technologies.*

Introduction.

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to Oliy Majlis, he said that "Improving the quality of education is the only correct way of development of new Uzbekistan." As our grandfather Yusuf Khos Hajib said: "Where there is intelligence, there is greatness, where there is knowledge, there is greatness." Therefore, we should continue the reforms we have started in this field, go to educational institutions, communicate more with teachers and trainers, and jointly solve the issues raised by them to improve the quality of educational work" (1)

In this sense, our state should fundamentally improve the quality of education in professional educational institutions, take into account the interests of students in these institutions, and allow young people to master the specialty of their choice in depth. Good goals such as creating conditions are being implemented. For this, the main task of improving the education system is to increase the quality of education.

Literature analysis.

What does the quality of education depend on? There are different approaches to the quality of education in the sources. Including:

The quality of education is a set of knowledge acquired in specific conditions, which is necessary to improve the quality of human life and achieve a specific goal (2).

The quality of education is considered to be a sum of educational elements that represent the level of satisfaction of the specified requirements of the individual, society and the state (3).

Based on modern requirements, that is, all factors that affect the quality and efficiency of education (state educational standards, curricula, teaching methods and technologies, educational didactic tools, etc.) revised, based on modern requirements, with the introduction of appropriate changes. One factor to improve the quality of education is the organization of smart education.

The adoption of the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 48 of January 18, 2019 "On approval of the concept of introduction of "Smart City" technologies in the Republic of Uzbekistan" is one of these works. The concept of the introduction of "Smart City" technologies includes the principle of "Smart Education", which includes a program of actions to create an innovative environment in education, taking into account future changes in the education system.

"Smart education" is a set of technological solutions in the form of educational online platforms and public open online courses, advanced visualization and remote access technologies filled with virtual reality, etc. (4).

The main part. During the introduction of market relations in the field of education, the concepts of "educational service market", "competition", "customer" appeared, describing socio-economic relations. At the same time, new approaches to education, organizational, economic, pedagogical, methodological and technological re-equipment are required. Therefore, in order to establish the activity of the educational system in completely new ways, there is a need to design a strategy of educational development based on the socio-economic characteristics of the educational institution in the country, and the dynamics of the educational service market. One of the effective ways to solve this problem is the traditional and global trends based on the scientific and innovative approaches. In fact, at present, great attention is paid to the social sphere, which is one of the important directions of the economic and social reforms of our republic, in particular, of the sphere of education and personnel training, and extensive reforms are being implemented in the continuous education system.

In recent years, on the basis of the innovative approach, there has been a need for various scientific researches on the development of innovative components of the educational system, innovative management of educational processes at different levels or stages, modeling of innovative processes, training of teachers for innovative activities. The most important factor necessary for the transition to the path of innovative development is not only the production of technical ideas, but also the production of products for domestic and foreign markets, as well as the training of highly qualified specialists in advanced educational institutions for its implementation. Education should be carried out with the help of existing methodological experience and innovative directions of educational practice. Supporting the leading role of theoretical and practical activities, which are innovative educational processes, is the basis for the development integration of pedagogical science and practice. The important social and professional qualities of the teacher's readiness for innovative activity are related not only to the economic and financial situation in the educational institution, but also directly to the demand for these qualities. Qualifications and professional qualities of professionally successful teachers are the main real requirements of modern education. Innovators-pedagogues are a requirement of today's education, and in order to reach professional heights, it is necessary to deepen their education in training and retraining courses. It is necessary for professors and teachers to widely spread their innovative activities, teach young teachers, and demonstrate interactive teaching methods in open classes. As a result, teachers have to find new ways of evaluating their activities, change their views on their profession, transform their pedagogical and creative abilities, i.e. teach others, and change the narrow concepts of teachers' professional functions.

Educational technology is a means to an end, which may or may not lead to the intended result. The level of achievement of the goal depends not only on the technology, but also on the

skill of the "technologist" (that is, the pedagogue). Technologization of teaching process is the process of transformation and introduction of specific innovative methods, tools, forms and their elements into the real teaching system, for example, the use of video films in learning and formation, the use of new computer programs in conducting experiments. All this represents the essence of modernization.

In recent years, the use of presentations prepared in Microsoft Power Macromedia Flash software packages with extensive use of multimedia tools in educational activities has become commonplace, but at the same time, such interactive technologies are entering the field of education that they are in the slide show category compressing presentations.

In ensuring the quality of education, the following can be applied to the auditorium in the educational institution, that is, the control and management of the lighting in the auditorium, the transfer of data to the management server for analysis, the transfer of information to the server and control of energy consumption in auditoriums with the possibility of further processing through software, control of temperature and humidity in the auditorium with the possibility of transferring climate data to the server, the possibility of transferring data to the fire alarm control panel, as well as to the control server. The above functionality, which includes monitoring the state of entrance doors and windows, etc., forms the concept of "Smart Audience".

"Smart Audience" is a collection of Internet-driven technical tools that can be used to manage audiences. The system consists of connecting various devices and controlling them.

"Smart auditorium" means the implementation of smart equipment technology in the auditorium. The essence of the smart audience is to create a network of modules to receive sensor readings and control elements of automatic devices, as well as to receive data and control a network of modules using hardware and software in manual or automatic mode (5).

It allows students to transfer information using new interactive equipment (interactive board - Smartboards, interactive display (Symposium), and allows the speaker to create presentations during the lesson itself. Interactive Smart, it is possible to display educational materials, give written comments on the image on the screen. At the same time, it is possible to save the information written on the interactive Smart Board on magnetic carriers, print them, and send them to the e-mail of the absent student. The educational material created on the Smart Board during the lecture can be recorded on the built-in video encoder and reused many times.

Today, of course, special software (Smart Notebook, Bridgit, Synhron Eyes) has been developed to make the most of the possibilities of interactive smart boards. Each of these software has its own capabilities. For example, Smart Notebook works with texts and objects, stores information, converts written letters into printed letters. The Bridgit program quickly and easily distributes presentations to partners in different parts of the world, receives reviews of its documents. To do this, the program will appear in the window of all conference participants in real time, as soon as the teacher highlights important positions in the speech on the common "desktop". Using the Synhron Eyes software package, the teacher can monitor all learners, screen and block learners' working monitors, send learning materials, textbooks, tests and the process using an interactive whiteboard can control.

In the process of working with interactive boards, the attention of all participants is concentrated and they begin to master the educational materials very quickly. As a result, the mastery rate of each participant increases. The introduction of new educational technology into

education ensures the transition of the educational scheme from a reproductive form to a creative form. Modern Smart education has two main goals:

1. To create a stable motivation for students to learn.
2. Searching for new forms and instruments of knowledge acquisition with the help of creative solutions.

So what is "Smart Education"? This is an association of educational institutions and teaching staff that implements education through a single Internet network based on common standards, agreements and technologies.

For this purpose, the establishment of "Intelligent audience" envisages the implementation of the following conditions:

- The auditorium should consist of a desk equipped with no more than 10-12 personal computers;
- Having a server with sufficient capacity at teacher's desk;
- Having an electronic board in the auditorium;
- The auditorium equipped with a web camera;
- All computers in the auditorium must be connected to the Internet and the ARM of the educational institution;
- All computers in the auditorium work in online mode;
- The auditorium should be a part of the local network of the educational institution; (the choice of the type of network topology is determined by the educational institution);
- The existence of a base of ETRs for conducting training sessions at a sufficient level at the ARM of the educational institution;
- Development of necessary tests to assess students' knowledge (the existence of a test base);
- Appropriate questions and tests developed by the teacher for each lesson depending on the size and complexity of the lesson;

- Programs of all modules should be revised and redeveloped depending on the categories of learners, which allows for differential training and assessment of learners depending on their knowledge potential.

Conclusion.

In the organization of teaching in this way, each subject teacher must carefully develop a training scenario and have tests that have an expert's opinion. If the mentioned actions are implemented, the high quality of the educational process will be ensured.

The teacher appears as the author, developer, researcher, user and promoter of new pedagogical technologies, theories, concepts.

The innovative activity of the teacher includes the analysis and evaluation of the innovation, the formation of the purpose and concept of future actions, the implementation and editing of this plan, and the assessment of effectiveness.

A modern teacher must meet necessary requirements in order to form an intelligent audience. As mentioned above, if the teacher organizes education based on innovation, the quality of professional education is ensured.

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